

ABSTRACT BOOK

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*SCIENCE-BASED SOLUTIONS IN TIMES OF CRISIS: INTEGRATING SCIENCE
AND POLICY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES.*

endosulfan and the microtubule assembly inhibitor herbicide benfluralin - in zebrafish embryos. In the present study, zebrafish embryos were exposed to different sublethal concentrations of endosulfan and benfluralin in a modified 96 hours zebrafish embryo toxicity test (zFET). Notably, no significant effects on survival or hatching rates were observed compared to the control group. However, transcriptomic analysis revealed distinct molecular responses in embryos exposed to each pesticide, delineating their specific impacts on biological processes. Benfluralin exposure led to differential expression of genes associated with muscle cell differentiation, heart contraction, and skeletal muscle development. Conversely, endosulfan exposure targeted genes crucial for hormone response, neuron apoptotic processes, and neuron death, pivotal for nervous system development. These findings highlight the intricacy of sublethal effects induced by these compounds on non-target organisms, emphasizing the need for a more comprehensive assessment beyond survival-focused evaluations. Integrating these molecular insights into risk assessment frameworks is imperative, especially in establishing transcriptomic points of departure (tPODs) protective against chronic effects. This integration recognises complexities beyond traditional endpoint measurements and provides additional weight-of-evidence for a more holistic assessment of pesticide toxicity.

1.05.P-Th010 In vitro assessment of the synergistic potentials of the ingredients in surface applied preservatives for dermal cytotoxicity and skin sensitization

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Wood preservatives are biocidal products used to protect wood used in building materials, furniture or consumer products. Consumers may be exposed to low concentrations of biocidal components on the skin through direct daily use of the products. Taking into account the dermal route of exposure, we attempted to determine the cytotoxicity and skin sensitization of single components and their mixtures contained in commercial wood preservatives. Three preservatives were selected because their ingredient information was available in a previously established biocidal product database in South Korea. As a first step, nine compounds were tested for their cytotoxicity using the HaCaT, skin keratinocytes. The compounds with EC₅₀ values less than 1,000 µM were included in binary or tertiary equitoxic mixtures, depending on whether these compounds were simultaneously present in the same preservative product. The EC_x value derived from the mixture toxicity test was compared with the EC_x value predicted by the concentration addition (CA) model to calculate the model deviation ratio (MDR) to determine the interaction between mixture components. We found that certain combinations showed synergism in the cytotoxicity assay, so as a further step we tried to confirm the mode of action and synergistic effects by the ARE-Nrf2 assay using KeratinoSensTM cell line based on OECD TG 442D. In the cytotoxicity test, five compounds showed EC₅₀ values of less than 1,000 µM, and a synergistic effect was observed with an MDR of 7.28 to 25.03 in a mixture containing a carbamate family compound. In the KeratinoSens assay, a synergistic effect was also observed in a carbamate compound containing mixtures. We confirmed that the synergistic interaction of a carbamate group biocidal compound was mediated by the second key event (KE) of the AOP (Adverse Outcome Pathway) for skin sensitization. Given the relatively high synergistic effect, further research and consideration of the hazards and interactions of the mixtures in commercial products is needed for the safety management of wood preservatives and related biocidal products.

1.05.P-Th011 In vitro Toxicity screening of real-life mixture using HepG2 cells

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To develop the risk prediction technology for mixture toxicity, a reliable and extensive dataset of experimental results is required. In everyday life, people are exposed to complex mixtures comprising more than ten compounds unintentionally, yet most published literature has only data in combinations with two or three substances. Therefore, there is a very limited dataset for predicting the toxicity of complex mixtures. On the other hand, complex mixtures may have different mode of actions (MoA) due to their variety of composition, posing difficulty in the prediction using conventional toxicity prediction models, i.e., concentration addition (CA) and independent action (IA) models. In this study, we aimed to generate an experimental dataset comprising complex mixtures. These mixtures were representative of our real-life exposure to be served as reliable dataset for developing the prediction model for mixtures with different MoA. To identify the target complex mixtures, we referred the findings of the HBM4EU project. We identified three groups of 7~10 substances that were commonly detected together in human bodies, namely environmental phenols, perfluorinated compounds, and heavy metal compounds, assuming them to have different MoA. Additionally, we added a separate mixture consisting of 9 organophosphate flame retardants (OPFRs) which may have a similar MoA. All target substances were tested for cytotoxicity using HepG2 cell lines and the EC₁₀ values were derived after 48-hrs exposure. Then, 50 different complex mixtures were generated with equitoxic mixtures of EC₁₀ levels, randomly selected. To determine the interaction effect, the model deviation ratio (MDR) was calculated by comparing the observed EC₁₀ with the predicted EC₁₀ from the CA model. These values were then categorized to the three types of interactions. Dose-response curves and EC₅₀ values were calculated for all complex mixtures. Out of 50 mixtures, none demonstrated synergism, while 6 mixtures exhibited antagonistic effect (MDRs 0.31~0.48). The remaining mixtures showed additivity (MDRs 0.50~1.34). Our experimental data has been formatted and constructed to the database. It will be used to conduct further research that aims to develop a novel two-stage mixture prediction model for application in the mixture risk assessment.

1.05.P-Th012 Apical and molecular endpoints in zebrafish embryos exposed to cadmium

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The EPIBOOST project aims at validating the epigenetic modifications caused by chemicals as biomarkers of relevance which can support more accurate environmental risk assessment. For this, a multiparametric approach is pursued by looking at effects of chemicals from the individual and biochemical levels to the transcriptomic and epigenetic levels, with the aim of establishing a link between phenotypic and molecular endpoints. In this work, taking cadmium (Cd) as case study, 96 hours zebrafish larvae were exposed to sublethal concentrations of Cd for 24 hours. Apical endpoints analysed included mortality, development, and swimming behaviour (swimming distance and path angles). At the same time, we analysed biochemical endpoints including biotransformation enzymes (glutathione-s-transferase (GST)), antioxidant enzymes (catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and glutathione reductase (GR)), oxidative damage markers (lipid peroxidation (LPO)), and neurotoxicity markers (acetylcholinesterase (AChE)). At concentrations tested no effects on survival or development (delays or anomalies were observed) and the antioxidant system did not seem to have been activated (no changes in GST, CAT, GPx or GR activities were detected). AChE was however inhibited suggesting neurotoxicity elicited by the tested Cd concentrations. This was further supported by changes in behavioural parameters at the last concentration tested namely changes in the proportion of rapid/slow movements and changes in the proportions of zigzag movements/straight movements. At present, we are performing transcriptomic and DNA methylation analysis to evaluate the effects of Cd exposure at the genomic level. In the near future we will integrate molecular and apical endpoints to identify biomarkers of exposure to cadmium. This data will contribute to understand the Cd adverse outcome pathway and validate epigenomic effects as a valuable tool to understand effects of contaminants at larger ecological scales.

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Keywords: *Danio rerio*, embryo development, locomotor behaviour, biomarkers, transcriptomics, DNA methylation

1.05.P-Th013 Molting inhibition in non-model species *Calanus finmarchicus* exposed to aquatic veterinary agents

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The Norwegian aquaculture industry is one of the most important industries in coastal areas and farmed Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) represents the second largest export in Norway. Control of threats to this economically important industry is important at both local and national levels. One of the largest threats to this industry is parasite infections of salmon from salmon louse (*Lepeophtheirus salmonis*). Chemotherapeutics and other strategies have been used to protect farmed fish in open-net pens from this parasite, one of them being the use of chitin synthesis inhibitors (CSI) such as teflubenzuron (TEF) and emamectin benzoate (EMB). TEF and EMB are among the most used feed-administered CSI. Although the adverse endpoints are similar, the compounds have different molecular modes of action. TEF inhibits the expression of the enzyme chitin synthase causing reduced chitin production and disrupted molting in immature stages of salmon louse. EMB on the other hand, has a neural inhibitory effect on the regulation of ecdysis causing the same endpoint as TEF. Thus, both these CSI have adverse effects on the molting process in salmon louse and are especially effective against the more molting frequent larval and pre-adult life stages. As chitin synthesis is an arthropod-specific process, CSI has low toxicity to vertebrates and algae. However, they are likely to have adverse effects on nontarget arthropod species such as the copepod *Calanus finmarchicus* a key species in the Northern Atlantic ecosystem. The aim of this project is to assess the sensitivity of *C. finmarchicus* to CSI exposure and uncover the causal relationships between CSI exposure and adverse effects. The objectives are to study CSI-mediated changes in chitin content, expression of genes related to molting (ecdysis), and imaging of structural deterioration of the copepod cuticle. Based on this information, a conceptual overview linking events together in relationships in an adverse outcome pathway (AOP) framework will be outlined. Preliminary results indicate that nauplii of *C. finmarchicus* display increased mortality at concentrations >200 times lower for teflubenzuron than emamectin benzoate, thus *C. finmarchicus* are much more sensitive to the teflubenzuron.

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1.05.P-Th014 A Gamechanger In The Mutagenicity Characterization of Azo Dyes

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Azo dyes, characterized by the functional group (-N=N-), are the most widely used dye class in several applications such as textiles, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and food. That is why studies on their mutagenicity have been carried out over the years. However, the uncertainty about their purities, solubility issues, and lack of molecular confirmation may have compromised

Apical and molecular endpoints in zebrafish embryos exposed to cadmium

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Multiparametric approaches can result in a more accurate environmental risk assessment of contaminants.

This can be pursued by looking at effects of chemicals from the individual and biochemical levels to the transcriptomic and epigenetic levels, with the aim of establishing a link between phenotypic and molecular endpoints.

Aim

Using zebrafish eleutheroembryos the aim of this work was to evaluate developmental, behavioural and biochemical effects to later relate to molecular effects resulting from **cadmium (Cd)** exposure.

TAKEAWAY

The integration of molecular and apical endpoints will allow the identification of biomarkers of exposure to cadmium. This data will contribute to understand the **Cd adverse outcome pathway** and validate epigenomic effects as a valuable tool to understand effects of contaminants at larger ecological scales.

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METHODS – CADMIUM EXPOSURE

96 hours post fertilization zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) eleutheroembryos exposed for 24 h to cadmium (Cd)

Preliminary range-finding tests were performed to determine LC₅₀ and EC₅₀ for swimming bladder effects. In subsequent tests concentrations used were NOEC (no observed effect concentration for swimming bladder effects), NOEC/3, NOEC/10, NOEC/30, NOEC/100 and control)

Developmental, biochemical and molecular endpoints: 10 organisms per well, 16 replicates (wells) per treatment

8 Pools of 10 organisms collected for determination of glutathione-s-transferase (GST), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and glutathione reductase (GR), lipid peroxidation (LPO), and acetylcholinesterase (AChE)

8 Pools of 10 organisms preserved for transcriptomic and DNA methylation analysis

At present, we are performing transcriptomic and DNA methylation analysis to evaluate the effects of Cd exposure at the genomic level

Behavioural endpoints: 24 organisms (individually exposed) per treatment

Basal locomotor activity and swimming patterns assessed using the **Zebrafish** video tracking system.

Swimming patterns evaluated through the larvae path angles

Classes of angles defined for the evaluation of larvae swimming pattern

Mortality and developmental endpoints

- ✓ LC₅₀ = 10.32 mg/L (standard error = 1.09)
- ✓ EC₅₀ = 34.38 µg/L (st err = 1.33x10⁸)

Behavioural endpoints

- ✓ Behavioural parameters showed at the highest concentration changes in the proportion of rapid/slow movements
- ✓ Changes in the proportions of zigzag movements (class 1 angles) and straight movements (class 4 angles) suggest effects in the fish swimming patterns

Biochemical endpoints

- ✓ AChE activity was decreased suggesting neurotoxicity elicited by the tested Cd concentrations
- ✓ The antioxidant system did not seem to have been activated (no changes in GST, CAT, GPx or GR activities were detected).
- ✓ No lipid peroxidation detected